

Nutrient and Anti-Nutrient Content of Wheat-Cassava Composite Flour

*Nwachukwu, Chinwe Adaobi¹, Enyi, Chukwunwike Uchenna¹, Ogbedeagu, Clara Obiageri¹ and Arukwe, Dorathy Chinomso²

¹Department of Food Science and Technology, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo. Imo State, Nigeria

²Department of Food Science and Technology, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike P.M.B 7267 Umuahia, Abia State Nigeria

Corresponding author: chinweadanwachukwu@gmail.com, 08063542418

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Abstract

This study evaluated the nutrient and anti-nutrient properties of wheat-cassava composite flour. Composite flour of cassava and wheat were blended into different ratios and analysed for nutrients and anti-nutrient properties. The results showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in the phytochemical properties of the flour samples. Vitamins and mineral contents of cassava flour at 100% had the highest (2.87mg/100g) content of vitamin C while 100% wheat flour sample had the least (0.97mg/100g). Vitamin C increased significantly ($p < 0.05$) with increase in the ratio of cassava flour in wheat-cassava composite flours. Wheat flour 100:0(W-C) contained the highest (0.56mg/100g) vitamin A and cassava flour 0:100(W-C) had the lowest (0.13mg/100g) vitamin A. The mineral values in wheat flour and cassava flour differed ($p < 0.05$) significantly. Cassava flour had a moisture content of 11.10% while wheat flour had a moisture content of 11.90%. The highest (2.96%) total crude ash content was recorded in wheat flour samples while the lowest (1.945%) was recorded in cassava flour. Addition of cassava to wheat in composite flour improved the nutrient compositions of the blends.

Keywords: Nutrient, anti-nutrient, wheat, cassava, composite flour.

INTRODUCTION

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) is widely known as the generally accepted cereal grains for bread and cakes production along with other pastries. Wheat flour is commonly used in bakery products as it provides a palatable, light and loaf of valuable sizes when processed into fermented dough (Amadeu et al., 2024). Wheat flour is made up of starch and protein which form the structure of the bread. Two types of proteins gliadin and glutenin exist in flour. Gliadin which is the prolamins of wheat, comprises of 40 – 50 % of proteins which are very sticky and inelastic. It gives dough its cohesive nature. The glutelins also called glutenins provides resistance to extension during mixing to form the elastic dough. The dough forms thin sheets that retain gas and produce light baked products (Li et al., 2024).

Cassava is a dicotyledonous plant which belongs to the family *Euphorbiaceae*. According to Cock (2002), cassava has been reported as an essential staple for more than 500 million people in the developing world. Majority of the world cassava production is being processed for human

consumption, as well as for livestock and starch production. Cassava is often regarded as poor people crop. This is as a result of some challenges of the crop such as lower protein content, cyanogenic glucosides present in the tuber and poor storage of the tubers (Alimi et al., 2024).

Composite flour technology refers to the process of mixing flours from different local raw material to produce food products of high quality in an economical way. Composite flour formulation is very important for manufacturing of value-added products with better functionality (Alimi et al., 2024)

Due to the high cost of wheat importation into Nigeria, which ultimately affects the prices of bakery products in the market, bakery industries have been seeking for alternatives to wheat in order to reduce cost of production. This study was carried out in order to explore the use of wheat-cassava composite flour. The objective of this study is to evaluate the nutrient and phytochemical properties of wheat-cassava composite flour.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Source of materials

Freshly sweet cassava (*Manihot esculenta*) tubers were harvested from the Crop Science Department farm at University of Agriculture and Environmental Science Umuagwo, Imo State. Twenty five (25 kg) of wheat flour (Golden Penny Prime) was purchased from bakery shops in Owerri, Imo State Nigeria.

Methods

Cassava flour production

A variety (farmer's pride) of sweet cassava (*Manihot esculenta*) tubers was processed into cassava flour according to the method by Onabolu and Bokanga, (1995).

Formulation of the flour samples

Wheat and cassava flours were blended at the ratio of 80WF:20CF, 90WF:10CF composite flours, also 100WF:0CF and 0WF:100CF. 100WF:0CF was used as the control and 90WF:10CF was used as the reference sample.

Determination of nutrient component of the flour

The proximate composition, vitamin and mineral components of the composite flour samples were determined according the method described by AOAC (2012)

Determination of anti-nutritional components of flours

The alkaloid, flavonoid, Saponin, oxalate, phytates, phenols and cyanide components of flours were determined by the method described by AOAC (2012). According to the method of AOAC (2005), the determination of the concentration of alkaloid in the flours was carried out using the alkaline precipitation gravimetric method, the flavonoid content was determined by the gravimetric method, cyanide content was determined by passing 10 g of the flour samples through No.20 sieve into 800 ml Kjeldahl flask and 200 ml of H₂O was added to determine the cyanide content, Saponin content of the sample was determined by double extraction gravimetric method, the concentration of phenols was determined using the folin-cio caltean colorimetric method and phytate was determined using The Folin-Denis spectrophotometric method. Oxalate was determined by Titration Method. This determination involved three major steps digestion, oxalate precipitation and permanganate titration.

Statistical analysis

Analysis of variance was used for the determination of significant differences ($p < 0.05$) among treatment means, and separation of means was carried out using the SPSS version 20.0. Separation of means was carried out by Duncan's Multiple range test, and values reported as means and standard deviation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Proximate composition of flour samples

The proximate values of the flour samples were presented in Table 1. The four flour samples contained moisture content in the range of 11.10-11.90% and the moisture content of the cassava flour sample 0:100 (W-C) was 11.10 %. Charles *et al.* (2005), Shittu *et al.* (2007) and NIS (2004) had respectively stated moisture content ranges of 9.2-12.3 % and 11.0 -16.0 % for cassava flour. According to Debraszczyk (2005), the optimum storage moisture level recommended for wheat is below 12.5 %. Moisture content is very important in the storage of flours; high levels above 12% allow for the growth of microorganisms and thus low levels are recommended to ensure extended shelf life stability (Harris and Koomson, 2011).

The fat contents of the flour samples were in the range of 0.60-1.50 %, with cassava flour having the lowest value (0.60 %). This is higher than 0.10 - 0.40 % previously reported for cassava flour by Charles *et al.* (2005). The wheat flour had 1.50 % fat which is within the range of 1.0-2.0% reported for wheat flour (Shewry and Hey, 2020). The low fat contents of the flour samples recorded in this study are indication that the flours will be less prone to lipid oxidation (rancidity).

The ash contents of the flour samples were in the range of 1.94 - 2.96 %. The highest (2.96 %) ash content was recorded for the wheat flour sample while the lowest (1.94 %) ash content was recorded for the cassava flour. Ash content gives an idea of the mineral contents in the food.

The protein contents of the flour samples were in the range of 0.59-12.20 %. Wheat flour had the highest (12.20 %) protein content while the cassava flour protein was the lowest (0.59 %). The protein contents of the wheat flour and wheat-cassava composite flour samples fall within the range 0.1-0.7% for cassava flour and (10-15 %) (Montagnac *et al.*, 2009). Wheat flour is widely used for bread making due to its gluten protein (Nwanekezi, 2013). The cassava flour does not contain gluten protein. Therefore, blending of wheat flour with cassava flour reduced the level of protein and the gluten protein of the composite flour samples 90:10 (W-C) and 80:20 (W-C).

The crude fibre contents of the flour samples ranged from 2.06 % to 3.18 %. The cassava flour had the highest (3.18 %) fibre content while the wheat flour fibre content was 2.06 %. The crude fibre content of the wheat flour was within the range of 1.5 - 2.5 % and 1.7 - 2.6 % by (Montagnac *et al.*, 2009). The crude fibre content of the cassava flour aids in bowel movement. Dietary fibre was reported to lower the risk of various disease conditions such as diverticulitis, cancer, diabetes, and constipation (Montagnac *et al.*, 2009).

The cassava flour sample 0:100 (W-C) had the highest (82.59 %) carbohydrate content and the wheat flour contained the lowest (69.38 %) carbohydrate value. The carbohydrate content of the wheat flour with a moisture content of 14 % was within the range of 54 to 62 % reported by Shittu *et al.* (2007). The carbohydrate content obtained for the wheat flour was higher probably due to the low moisture content of the sample. Carbohydrate is a good source of energy and makes fuel

available for proper functioning of the brain (Zvinavashe et al., 2011). The major function of carbohydrate is to supply the body's cell with needed glucose, which is the form our body absorbs carbohydrate for energy use (Shittu et al., 2007). Carbohydrate also maintains blood glucose levels and also plays a role in gastrointestinal health (Zvinavashe et al., 2011).

Table 1. Proximate composition of flour samples

Flour sample (%)	Moisture	Ether extract	Ash	Protein	Crude Fibre	Carbohydrate
80:20 W-C	11.75±0.04 ^a	1.30±0.01 ^a	2.76±0.01 ^c	9.88±0.01 ^c	2.28±0.02 ^b	72.03±0.02 ^b
90:10 W-C(Ref.)	11.80±0.01 ^a	1.40±0.02 ^a	2.86±0.03 ^b	11.04±0.04 ^b	2.17±0.02 ^c	70.73±0.04 ^c
100:0 W-C(Cont.)	11.90±0.02 ^a	1.50±0.01 ^a	2.96±0.01 ^a	12.20±0.03 ^a	2.06±0.04 ^d	69.38±0.04 ^d
0:100 W- C	11.10±0.01 ^b	0.60±0.03 ^b	1.94±0.02 ^d	0.59±0.02 ^d	3.18±0.02 ^a	82.59±0.08 ^a
LSD	0.33	0.28	0.021	0.031	0.03	0.082

Values are means±standard deviations from the means. Mean scores with different superscript letter(s) on the same column are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

Key:

80:20 (W-C) = 80% wheat flour + 20% cassava flour

90:10 (W-C) (Ref.) = 90% wheat flour + 10 % cassava flour (Reference sample)

100:0 (W-C) (Cont.) = 100% wheat flour (control flour sample) 0:100 (W-C) = 100% cassava flour

LSD = Least significant difference

Vitamins and mineral composition of the flour samples

The results of this findings revealed that 100 % cassava flour 0:100 (W-C) had the highest (2.87 mg/100 g) content of vitamin C while 100 % wheat flour sample 100:0 (W-C) had the least (0.97 mg/100 g) value as presented in (Table 2). Vitamin C increased significantly ($p < 0.05$) with increase in the ratio of cassava flour in the wheat-cassava composite flours. Blending of cassava flour with wheat flour increased the vitamin C content of the resulting wheat-cassava composite flour. Vitamin C is very important in metabolism of iron and as well fight against iron deficiency anaemia (Akubor, 2011). However, the wheat flour sample 100:0 (W-C) contained the highest 0.56 mg/100 g) amount of vitamin A while the 100 % cassava flour sample 0:100 (W-C) had the lowest (0.13 mg/100 g) vitamin A content. This resulted to lower vitamin A values in the wheat-cassava composite flours. Vitamin A is an antioxidant; it plays a vital role in controlling total metabolic reaction in the body (Abiaka et al., 2012). This vitamin is also important for maintenance of healthy skin and hair, bone growth, good visual sight, reproduction and mucous membranes (FAO, 2005).

The low content of calcium in cassava flour is a disadvantage for its use for the baking of bread. Calcium plays a vital role in bread making. It performs the role of yeast nutrient and regulating pH level for dough conditioners. When it is in limited supply, it can be added as a dietary supplement to improve the calcium content of the baked product (Mason, 2011). Like calcium, the magnesium content of the wheat flour was highest and was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than

those of other three flour samples. The cassava flour had the lowest (51.0 mg/100 g) magnesium content. Compositing of wheat flour with cassava flour reduced both the calcium and magnesium values in the flours. Magnesium performs over 300 biochemical reactions in the body. It plays an important role in maintaining normal muscle function and nerve, supports a healthy immune system, steady the heartbeat, and helps for stronger bones. It also helps in blood glucose level regulation and aids in energy and protein production (Dean, 2007).

Wheat flour had a potassium value (168.0 mg/100 g) which was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than other flour samples. Potassium allows human cells to have the needed fluid balance they require to work very well (Mason, 2011). However, the iron content of the cassava flour sample was the highest and was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than those of the other three flour samples. Iron is an important mineral needed in our bodies. It helps with the movement of oxygen to the cells where it is needed. It is part of the pigment called haemoglobin in the red blood cell (Pressman, 2007). Zinc was also highest in the wheat flour. The cassava flour had very low zinc. Zinc is found in cell throughout the body. It helps in the body's defensive system. It also plays a major role in the breakdown of carbohydrate, cell division, senses of smell and taste and growth and wound healing (Mason, 2011).

Formation of bones and teeth is the main function of phosphorus in the body (Pressman, 2007). It plays a vital role in the use of carbohydrates and fats in the body. It is also required for protein production in the body which is needed for growth, maintenance and repair of cells and tissue (Mason, 2011). Generally, cassava flour contains lower minerals contents than wheat flour and it affected the mineral contents of the wheat-cassava composite flours.

Table 2: Vitamin C, Vitamin A and Mineral contents of the flour samples

Flour samples	Vitamin C	Vitamin A	Calcium	Magnesium	Potassium	Iron	Zinc	Phosphorous
80:20 (W-C)	1.35±0.02 ^b	0.47±0.02 ^c	26.1±0.70 ^d	67.0±0.00 ^d	159.3±0.14 ^c	2.13±0.07 ^b	5.08±0.07 ^d	3.13±0.04 ^b
90:10 (W-C)	1.16±0.02 ^d	0.52±0.02 ^b	29.1±0.70 ^b	68.6±0.41 ^b	163.7±0.70 ^b	1.94±0.03 ^c	5.64±0.02 ^b	2.99±0.06 ^c
100:0 (W-C)	0.97±0.05 ^d	0.56±0.01 ^a	32.0±0.0 ^a	70.50±0.70 ^a	168.0±0.14 ^a	1.75±0.07 ^d	6.20±0.14 ^a	3.31±0.01 ^a
0:100 (W-C)	2.87±0.03 ^a	0.13±0.01 ^d	2.50±0.70 ^c	51.0±0.41 ^c	124.50±0.12 ^d	3.63±0.03 ^a	0.58±0.03 ^c	2.43±0.03 ^d
LSD ($p < 0.05$)	0.038	0.002	0.632	0.949	1.643	0.059	0.08	0.038

Values are means±standard deviations from the means. Mean scores with different superscript letter(s) on the same column are significantly difference ($p < 0.05$). LSD=Least Significant Different ($p < 0.05$)

Key:

80:20 (W-C) = 80% wheat flour + 20% cassava flour

90:10 (W-C) (Ref.) = 90% wheat flour + 10 % cassava flour (Reference sample)

100:0 (W-C) (Cont.) = 100% wheat flour (control flour sample) 0:100 (W-C) = 100% cassava flour

LSD = Least significant difference

Anti-nutritional factors in the flour samples

The Anti-nutritional values of the flour samples were presented in Table 3. There were significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in the saponin, alkaloid, phenol, tannin, oxalate and cyanide contents of the flour samples as presented. Cassava flour recorded high values in saponin, flavonoids, alkaloids phenols and cyanide contents but blending with wheat flour to form wheat- cassava composite flour brought reduction in these values. Saponins are anti-nutrients but small amount in foods is needed. Saponins have antitumor and anti-mutagenic activities which can help lower the risk of cancers in humans by preventing the growth of cancer cells (Rao *et al.*, 1995). Flavonoids are group of phenolic compounds that include tannins. These compounds chelate metals like iron and zinc which reduce the absorption of these nutrients, inhibit the activities of the digestive enzymes and may precipitate proteins (Beecher, 2003). Some alkaloids have effects on the development of offspring of animals that consume them. However, alkaloids have so many pharmacological activities which including anticancer, anti-malarial, anti-hyperglycaemia and stimulant activities (Emmanuel *et al.*, 2012).

The phytate affects the nutritional value of foods by interfering with the bioavailability of mineral, proteins and as well carbohydrates (MacDonald *et al.*, 2012). Phytic acid binds with minerals such as magnesium, iron, calcium, zinc and copper. Phenol serves as an antioxidant and its availability in foods is linked with different salutary effects in humans. It inhibits inflammatory effects like coronary artery diseases (Cooke, 2002). Tannin also decreases the availability and digestion of other nutrients present in the diet. It forms complexes with digestive agents, which result in reduced enzyme activity and nutrient digestibility (Cooke, 2002).

Oxalic acid reacts with cations like calcium and iron in the body to form crystals of the corresponding oxalates which are removed in urine as minute crystals. These oxalates form larger kidney stones that can affect the kidney tubules (Wobeta *et al.*, 2007).

Cyanide is a toxic compound which is found in cassava. High content of cyanide results to several diseases such as tropical ataxic neuropathy and konzo. Prolong consumption of diet which contains cyanide especially among populations with poor nutritional status, results to these diseases (Hahn, 1989). The range of cyanide in the flour samples was (0.7-1.43%) or (7.0-14.3 mg/kg). The cyanide contents of the wheat-cassava composite flour samples were 0.70 % and 0.78 % respectively and that of the wheat flour was 0.62 % and these levels are lower than 1.0 % (10 mg/kg) regarded as safe level by FAO/WHO (Adindu *et al.*, 2003). The anti-nutrients in the composite flour were at safe levels in this work.

Table 3. Anti-nutritional factors in the flour samples

Flour samples (%)	Saponin	Flavonoid	Alkaloid	Phytic acid	Phenol	Tannin	Oxalate (mg/g)
80:20 (W-C)	0.92±0.02b	3.71±0.03b	2.18±0.02b	4.81±0.02b	6.82±0.02b	1.18±0.02 ^c	0.83±0.02 ^c
90:10 (W-C)(Ref.)	0.83±0.03 ^c	3.67±0.02 ^b	1.49±0.17 ^c	4.84±0.03 ^{ab}	6.59±0.04 ^c	1.21±0.02 ^b	0.42±0.02 ^b
100:0 (W-C)	0.74±0.01 ^d	3.63±0.04 ^b	0.80±0.02 ^d	4.87±0.03 ^a	6.36±0.03 ^d	1.24±0.02 ^a	0.45±0.0 ^a
0:100 (W-C)	1.63±0.04 ^a	4.04±0.01 ^a	7.68±0.01 ^a	4.59±0.02 ^c	8.67±0.03 ^a	0.94±0.07 ^d	0.11±0.02 ^d

LSD(p<0.05)	0.026	0.138	0.081	0.03	0.036	0.019	0.019
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Values are means±standard deviations from the means. Mean scores with different superscript letter(s) on the same column are significantly difference (p<0.05). LSD=Least Significant Different (p<.0.05)

Key:

80:20 (W-C) = 80% wheat flour + 20% cassava flour

90:10 (W-C) (Ref.) = 90% wheat flour + 10 % cassava flour (Reference sample)

100:0 (W-C) (Cont.) = 100% wheat flour (control flour sample) 0:100 (W-C) = 100% cassava flour

LSD = Least significant difference

CONCLUSIONS

The inclusion of cassava at levels up to 20% into wheat to form wheat-cassava composite flour improved some of the quality attributes of the flour in this study. It was observed that cassava flour contained a lot of vitamin C which is lacking in wheat flour and its use in composite with wheat improved the quality of the composite flour. Vitamin C being very vital in iron metabolism and subsequent fights against iron deficiency anaemia, therefore using this composite flour in food production will improve this deficiency. Also, compositing wheat with cassava flour brought a reduction in the fat content which suggests that the flour and products from it will be less prone to lipid related forms of deterioration. Cassava flour was found to be very rich in dietary fibre which was evident in the composite flour. Therefore, the composite products will be of immense health benefits especially in weight loss, and diabetes management. Finally, inclusion of 20% or more of cassava flour into wheat to form wheat-cassava composite flour should be well adopted by food processor to boost food security in the nations.

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